

Research Article

Business Information Ethics Disclosure

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Abstract: Ethics is crucial for businesses to employ since it can come in handy in decision-making processes about what is right or wrong, it educates about how to act in a particular situation and creates a judgment to indicate better choices. Given that ethics appears as a code of conduct, it is intended to be agreed upon and adopted by all businesses. The issue that seeks to be addressed in the paper is to conceal the business's concern with the set of principles that determines the bounds of acceptable action (ethics). The paper aims in disclosing the issues from real cases and strategies to gain outstanding ethics in managing business policies and practices. Impacts towards the paper could lead to better awareness for the business in applying appropriate ethical aspects to their practices. The study discovered that social entrepreneurs, employment contracts, and corporate governance all encounter ethical issues while carrying out their duties. The researchers give solutions that can assist businesses in implementing effective ethics.

Keywords: ethics; business; social entrepreneur; employment contract; corporate governance.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Ethics instructs people how to behave in certain circumstances and helps them make decisions that have advantages for them personally. Not to be mistaken with laws, a society's moral code is made up of a number of interconnected laws that together convey the ethical principles that underlie society. Moreover, ethics comprises guidelines and principles that inform people to behave properly. The breach of ethics may result in unclear or no punishment or penalty since no restrictions to it. Over the past 10 years, businesses have paid increasingly more attention to encouraging moral and responsible digital design (Truax, C., Orchard, A. & Love, H. A., 2021).

In contrast to information technology, ethical concerns have had a positive and negative impact on business. First and foremost, spam email marketing offers the business the opportunity to communicate with millions of partners, organisations, and stakeholders globally at a very low cost. Employees, representing an important resource of any organization (Mehrotra, A. & Mariam, S., 2020), may also be observed at work while having access to their email and the Internet. The benefits make it possible for staff to balance their need for privacy and autonomy with the management of key corporate resources and working hours. On the other hand, the bad side of complying with ethical issues in information technology could include the case where the hackers could break into databases of financial

and retail institutions to steal customer information, then use it to commit theft by opening new accounts and charging purchase to unsuspecting victims. Students around the world have been caught downloading materials from the Web and plagiarizing content for their term papers. After all, only industries with core competences can effectively govern ethical and legal decision-making processes in their environment (Dhirani, L. L., Noorain Mukhtiar, Chowdhry, B. S., & Newe, T, 2023).

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The researcher is using the literature review method for this study. Research papers were observed and analysed. The research papers being referred to were precisely and strictly filtered according to the narrower aspect of ethics relating to business whereby the issues and strategies that appear to course from real cases. Moreover, in getting a more accurate journal to refer to, the researcher applies the Boolean research method. In delivering the arguments on the case, the researcher conceptualized the different parties to issues related to ethics on business including social entrepreneurs, contract employees and corporate governance. Then, there are strategies that could lead to better ethical development for business.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 *Ethical challenges that businesses are facing with examples from actual cases*

The researchers came across the fact that the implied ethical practices of various businesses varied. The significance of indicating them in the first place could enhance the business' working environment, as employees would feel more at ease accomplishing their duties in such a controllable ethical setting. Recently, the need for job seekers is more focused on a positive and healthy work environment, which implies the necessity for ethical procedures. Employees, on top of that, have the right to demand an exceptional business for putting their efforts and attention, spending daylight and night in, since choices are always accessible. Businesses are responsible for managing their employees' satisfaction with the ethical sides of their work environment in order to create excellent outcomes for the business and, most importantly, to secure their success. Employees in one business surely differ and sort in a variety of manners depending on their work of expertise. However, the remainder of this section aims for three parties with their own challenges faced in regard to ethical issues which include, social entrepreneurs, employment contracts and corporate governance.

3.1.1 *Dilemmas faced by social entrepreneurs in addressing social and commercial missions*

For the first challenge, it seems that many perceive social enterprises as a moral alternative to businesses (Bhatt, 2022). To support their operations, social entrepreneurs engage in economic activities to address difficult societal challenges. Since the interference demand from top management, stakeholders, and partners might flip everything completely upside down, the commercial department's scope of work is heavier than anyone could ever assume. The employee in charge was required to construct appropriate, efficient, and effective commercial procedures in response to the demands of today's customers and technology diversions. With so many rivals, being inventive alone will not suffice to win the market. Platforms for commercials are also necessary for reaching the proper target market.

In order to accomplish their social and economic goals, social entrepreneurs must overcome obstacles such as those linked to community engagement and juggling a variety of stakeholders. The study by Hota P.K. et. al (2023), with the aim of explicating, refining, and complementing the emerging theory of ethics in social entrepreneurship using 36 months of an ongoing qualitative and inductive study, of a SE (Alpha), those businesses in Uttarakhand, a rural area of India, provided the arguments for the challenges mentioned. The study's arguments will be outlined and suggested for better instances of business challenges involving the ethical component. In this specific case, the researchers aim to validate the moral conundrums that the study team, Alpha, known also as the social entrepreneur, has with respect to the rural Indian community.

a) Challenges in engaging the community

Entrepreneurs are expected to be prominent in the community since they can produce and invent new ideas, services, and business procedures, plan and establish a business based on their new ideas, and identify market possibilities. The Alpha team, as the social entrepreneur, had challenges involving the community in their full collaboration in managing social-commercial conflicts in this setting. First and foremost, in selecting beneficiaries, it was assumed that the community studied had limited and varying levels of access to resources. In comparison to small farmers, large farmers appear to enjoy higher revenue and assistance from other beneficiaries. Furthermore, if the Alpha team included women, sustainable development goals may be accomplished. However, due to gender inequality and patriarchal traditions, women are excluded from decision-making processes linked to farming and are either landless or own a small plot of land. Second, the absence of livelihood options in the communities where they were operating presented the Alpha team with moral conundrums in their scaling choice, which prevented them from fulfilling their social purpose or resolving their social-commercial goal.

The lesson learned from the findings obtained for the social entrepreneurs' first challenge in engaging the community in achieving their goals includes the limitations for the business in achieving their goals due to humanity's struggles, the culture they implied, and the environment they are exposed to. The business must identify more accurate ethical practices that are appropriate for its corporate goals. The rules followed by their target market will also have an impact on the business's ethics. After all, business ethics should be beneficial to the community in the geographical areas.

b) Challenges in balancing diverse stakeholders

In the context of the Alpha team trying to get the trust of a variety of stakeholders, there are some challenges they went through and most of them seem as if they could not be solved. The thinking between businesses or teams with their stakeholders definitely differs since the concept consists of many thinkers. It forms a combination of ideas from many experts. On top of that, knowing the importance of stakeholders to the business, mainly are increasing the chances of project success and broadening the pool of people who care about the well-being of your company.

According to the real case research, the Alpha team, known as a group of social entrepreneurs once again highlighted the challenges they faced while balancing social-commercial tensions which is in balancing diverse stakeholders. In summary, community members, angel investors, and government policymakers, as their stakeholders, are the ones that decided on providing resources and support to Alpha. On the other hand, the report said they were only interested in social impact stories, and less concerned about Alpha's data-driven approaches in the first place. It is best to conclude that the study

thought about the importance of knowing the differences between ethics of justice and ethics of care. The differences are as follows;

Table 1. The difference between ethics of justice and ethics of care.

Ethics of justice	Ethics of care
Suggests that while making decisions, an organization should depend on formal logic and unbiased judgement.	Suggests that ethical decision-making is influenced by the narrative and contextual intricacies of interpersonal interactions.

3.1.2 *Legal issues relating to employment contracts.*

Work done for another person that is expected to be done just for remuneration under the conditions of an employment contract is known as "conducted within the terms of an employment contract." Both parties' interests are protected by the employment contract. An agreement not to compete may be included in the employment contract by the employer to prevent the employee from using sensitive information for personal gain. In actuality, a strong work ethic triumphed over knowledge, training, and effort. This demonstrates the growing significance of work ethic in the employment process. The Bureau of Labour Statistics (2019) listed the activities of a human resource professional as recruit, screen, interview, and place workers.

The leadership of the workforce shifted as mills and factories expanded quickly from focusing on craftsmanship to maximising productivity. Cycles of long, uninterrupted workdays and feverish activity were countered by economic downturns and an increase in unemployment. There are moral requirements for all government contracting activity in the procurement regulations. When asked to sign a non-compete or non-disclosure agreement on the "take it or leave it" premise, employees may assume this is unethical because they aren't given any negotiating leverage. An organization's reputational value is taken into account while estimating its worth. Non-compete and confidentiality agreements' worth.

Most employment agreements aren't intended to be long-term. Even if an employment contract only lasts for a short time, there may be circumstances when both parties need to end their job connection.

Problems arise from employment contracts is lack of willingness. This problem is typically caused by higher-ranking workers abusing their power. In one of the real-life instances, Ms. Druyun, a Key Administrator, recruited the Boeing Company by giving the maker of aeroplanes significant contracts in order to secure work for herself, her daughter, and her daughter's fiancé (later son-in-law). She sent Boeing sensitive information from other companies in an effort to obtain a new job after she retired, and Boeing utilised it in their offers. Due to her acts, her accomplice was also imprisoned, and the president of Boeing resigned as a result. Boeing-related contracts are still being looked into. Actually, a \$615 million deal with the US Government on ethical complaints, in major part, For the second quarter of 2006, Boeing recorded a loss of \$160 million. She was the team member who understood the rules for the government contracting game the best. When faced with hiring someone who also offers a serious hazard due to unethical behaviour, Michael Sears, a former criminal who donated his knowledge and experience to the business, became the private sector example of what not to do.

3.1.3 Bribery and Corruption in business ethics

Offering, giving, receiving, or soliciting something of value in order to influence the behaviour of a person in a position of power constitutes bribery and corruption, both of which are immoral acts. Individuals, businesses, and society may suffer significantly as a result of these activities. In terms of corporate ethics, bribery and corruption damage trust, impair fair competition, and impede economic growth. These were considered to be the largest corporate governance scandals. Decision-makers, according to Petrick and Scherer (2003), had disregarded integrity's importance, nature, and potential.

Most nations consider bribery and corruption to be crimes, and they frequently have laws specifically prohibiting them. In Malaysia, The Malaysian Anti-Corruption Commission Act 2009 (the "MACC Act"), which was passed to establish the Malaysian Anti-Corruption Commission and to make additional and improved provisions for the prevention of corruption as well as for matters necessary and related thereto, is the main piece of legislation that governs bribery and corruption in Malaysia. The Anti-Corruption Act of 1997 has been replaced with the MACC Act. Its purpose is to encourage the honesty and decency of public and private sector management and to inform the public, public officials, and public authorities about corruption and its negative repercussions.

Rest (1986) defined moral awareness as an interpretive process through which people can identify difficulties that are real and related to specific situations. It is strongly tied to how one's conduct is formed. Religions or beliefs that place a great emphasis on morality will have a stronger moral foundation than others (Ward and King, 2018). There are various forms of bribery and corruption in business. Here are some examples of bribery that involves in business such as petty bribery. It involves small-scale payments to people in low-ranking positions to hasten the completion of routine activities or obtain essential services. Next is Grand corruption: Involves widespread acts of bribery at the top of the political or business food chain to sway crucial choices, agreements, or policies. Next is facilitation payments. It is when payments are paid informally to speed up or guarantee the completion of mundane tasks, frequently in nations with excessive bureaucracy. Another thing is when a person in a position of authority demands a bribe under the fear of negative repercussions, this is called extortion. Last is kickbacks. It is an unlawful payment or perks offered in exchange for preferential treatment, such as choosing to award contracts or make purchases.

There are actual examples of corruption and bribery. The 2009 accounting fraud by the founder of Satyam provides evidence that such conduct is motivated by greed, ambition, and a desire for fame, money, power, and glory. The situation shows that it is urgently necessary to strengthen corporate governance, ethics, accounting standards, and audits. Next, White-collar crime is on the rise, which calls for strong and exemplary punishment as well as efficient law enforcement conducted with the proper attitude (Bhasin, 2013). Based on these issues, ethics plays a significant role in determining how a person behaves as a result of accounting. Systems can be purposefully created by accountants to change people's behavior. They also more often represent the idea that accountability includes factors like attitudes and how other people utilize information, in addition to straightforward measurement and aggregation (Hofstede and Kinard, 1970). Therefore, it is crucial to investigate accounting conduct and lessen deviant attitudes that influence subsequent behavior.

Bribery will also have consequences and an impact on business ethics. First, bribery gives those who are ready to pay an unfair advantage, undermining honest and open competition. Second is the impact on economic costs. Corruption can drain resources away from profitable endeavours, preventing investment and economic growth. Third is lack of legitimacy and trust. Public trust in institutions, both public and private, is eroded by widespread bribery, which also calls into question their authority. Apart from that it also causes a Social inequality. Resources meant for the general welfare may be exploited or diverted to benefit a select few people or organizations, which can worsen social inequities. Next is impaired development. Poverty, poor governance, and insufficient access to

critical services such as education, healthcare, and other services are frequent problems in nations with high levels of corruption. It is crucial for people, companies, and governments to take a proactive approach against bribery and corruption in order to encourage ethical business practices. We can all work together to promote openness, responsibility, and a culture of honesty in order to promote equitable and long-term economic growth.

4. DISCUSSION

Figure 1. Conceptual Model

4.1 Strategies in applying ethics in managing business policies and practices

4.1.1 Applying idiosyncratic deals (i-deals)

In particular, everyone in the company, starting with the management, is required to devote great attention to ethical instruments aligned with the business in order to create influential and appropriate practices to operate the business. Employee satisfaction and organisational drive have an impact on the processes and viability of the business, consequently, customers could benefit from the strategic initiatives and customer service offered. Bal and Boehm, 2019, found a positive relationship between i-deals and customer satisfaction.

Effective and efficient ethics should be used to improve business performance. By using idiosyncratic (i-deals), voluntary, unique contracts of a nonstandard character are established with specific employees and their employers on terms that are advantageous to each side. According to Vizcaíno, F. V. et. al. (2023), when the workplace has a high ethical standard, employees are prone to believe that negotiates were given to those that deserved and earned special treatment. I-deals include schedule and task agreements, which can benefit both the employee and the business at large (Rosen et al., 2013). This explains why different sorts of arrangements are used in i-deals. Task i-deals are agreements formed between employees and their employers relating to changing the job's content or avoiding certain job responsibilities, whereas schedule i-deals refer to an employee's flexible daily work hours and focus on the employee's capacity to negotiate a flexible work schedule. After all, schedule i-deals and task i-deals may be advantageous to both the employee and the business in general.

4.1.2 *Using code ethics in business organizations*

A code of ethics defined as a distinct and formal document containing a set of prescriptions developed by and for a company to guide present and future behaviour on multiple issues for at least its managers and employees toward one another, the company, external stakeholders, and or society in general. (Kaptein and Schwartz, 2008, p. 113). When the company has a stated code of ethics, everyone is able to work the same rules in the organization, from the people at the top of the organisation, those in the executive suite, to the lowest member of the team. That also applies to consultants and contractors. A code of ethics helps in defining the company's identity and supports every aspect of its mission. The points of view from different stakeholders can be used to investigate the CE quality, as well as the employees of those stakeholders. As an example, an organisation that applies a code of ethics will be aware of the value of the document as a source of ethical culture and will be able to assess its potential impact on employees' ethical thinking and behaviour.

When employees are faced with a dilemma regarding ethics, it is their duty to Respond. The following decision-making model can be used to determine whether or not a specific course of action is "the right thing to do." Remember that doing nothing is an action in and of itself, and that action can have a negative impact on the Company and its personnel. Keep in mind that rushed decisions and work stress often have an ethical influence.

One of the factors affecting changes in corporate codes of ethics, may be seen in the coming together ability in the contents of codes of ethics (Berenbeim, 2000). The establishment of corporate subsidiaries throughout the world has forced the contents to be responsive to ethical issues on a more global scale.

A code of ethics established by professional licensing organisations must be followed by professionals like engineers, architects, and others. Licences may be cancelled by the giving organisation if someone does not follow the code, even though violations of these codes are not enforceable in court. As a result, professionals in many fields are held to standards of professional accountability in addition to the contracts they sign. The level of disclosure is another element of ethical standards that has been studied by researchers. In other words, an organization's attention to ethics and ethical issues can be judged by the accessibility its code of ethics is to all of its (Bondy et al., 2004).

4.1.3 *Strong legal framework*

Governments should pass comprehensive legislation that makes bribery and corruption illegal and guarantees that it is properly enforced. The legislation should apply to both the public and private sectors, and violators should face harsh consequences. A comprehensive set of laws, rules, and policies that control businesses' ethical behaviour and advance ethical and sustainable business practices is referred to as a solid legal structure in business ethics. It sets out a set of guidelines and requirements that companies must follow in order to ensure fairness, openness, and accountability in their operations.

Next is strong anti-corruption regulations and enforcement procedures should be a part of the legal structure in order to combat corruption in business. Along with whistleblower protections and procedures for reporting and looking into allegations of corruption, these laws might contain clauses that penalize bribery, embezzlement, money laundering, and other corrupt practices.

5. CONCLUSION

Business ethics encourages transparency, honesty, fairness, and integrity in all business interactions, both internal and external. It involves observing and maintaining the rights and well-being of all stakeholders, including employees, clients, suppliers, and other stakeholders. Businesses can develop strong relationships with their stakeholders and earn their trust by acting ethically, which will improve their reputation and increase customer loyalty.

In summary, businesses that are sustainable and profitable must stick to business ethics. Businesses can create trust, promote good connections, give back to society, abide by the law, and ensure their long-term success in an ever-changing business environment by respecting ethical standards.

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